

Employee motivation and service quality of Nigeria Police force in the South-South, Nigeria

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This study examined the relationship between employee motivation and Service Quality of Nigeria Police Force in the South-South region of Nigeria .A cross sectional research design was adopted for the study. The target population comprises of the entire officers and men of Nigeria police force (NPF) in the South-South Geo-Political region of Nigeria. 52,579 Census Population was applied Taro Yamen formula was employed to determine the sample size of 397. Two hundred and nine (209) copies of questionnaire were valid and analyzed out of the three hundred and ninety seven (397) copies of questionnaire distributed; descriptive statistics were employed in analyzing the demographic data of respondents as well as percentage frequencies for univariate analysis; also, Structural Equation Modeling from Analysis of Moment Structure version 20. Tool utilized to examine the relationship between the dimensions of employee motivation and the measures of Service Quality and to test hypotheses postulated for the research and multivariate level analysis was reported to ascertain moderating effect of organizational culture on the relationship between the predictor and criterion variables. The findings revealed that the dimensions of employee motivation as reviewed in extensive research such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation significantly associates with Service Quality measures adaperd. It was then concluded that employee motivation undoubtedly contributes to enhance Service Quality of Nigeria Police Force. Therefore, it was recommended that efforts should be made to boost of motivational Techniques employed in the Nigeria Police Force by paying special attention to salary and fringe benefits, job security and provision of better working facilitie and conditions , for these will enhance Service Quality of the Nigeria Police Force in the South –South region of Nigeria..

Keyword: Employee Motivation, Service Quality (SQ) and Nigeria Police Force (NPF).

INTRODUCTION

The significance of service Quality (SQ) in any organizational setting and work environment, including law enforcement cannot be over-emphasized. This is due to the fact that Service Quality has the tendency to influence customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, business performance and profitability. SQ is usually defined as a measure of how well the delivered services level matches customer's expectations (Santos, 2003).

Nowhere else is this more factual and important than in law enforcement profession (Ogunsina, 2011). Every organization ranging from small to large organization is very dependent on employees to meet their targets, achieve their visions and remain in the competition. Sevice quality could be technical or functional or image (Gronroos, 1982, 2001), physical, corporate and interactive, (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1982) service product, service environment, and service delivery (Rust & Oliver, 1994); interaction quality, physical environment quality, and outcome quality (Brady & Cronin, 2001).

Furthermore, scholars recognize that the motivation of

employees and Service Quality with work has a significant impact on organizational commitment and there are varying perspectives on what motivates various types of employees (Hill & Wiens-Tuers, 2002). With the recognition that this is not enough to bring about motivation expressed in Service Quality, other perspectives emerged giving particular importance to the training and skills development of employees (Woodruffe, 2000) applied through the underlying principle of continuous organizational learning. Since this covers only an aspect of human resource management; a holistic approach emerged that targets the development of a certain quality of employment life that covers fair wages, benefits, other employment conditions, and career development to support the facilitation of motivation and Service Quality directed towards organizational justice (Champion-Hughes, (2001).

Onuoha (2016) expressed motivation as an area of directing function, which covers all activities of managers that tend to align employee and organizational interests so that behaviour of organizational members results in the achievement of employee needs/wants simultaneously with the attainment of organizational goals. Onuoha opined that motivation can be looked at from either positive or negative perspective. Positive motivation includes; salary, increment, bonuses, promotion and praise. Negative motivation, often referred to as the stick approach uses penalties or punishments, often to induce a desired behaviour. When employees believe their organization is being fair when it comes to intrinsic reward and extrinsic they commit to organizational performance and long-term development and thus their Service Quality is improved

Thus the Police Force will deliver quality Services as expected by citizenry and the Organization they represent if they are highly motivated in terms of working conditions facilities, Salary structure, Fringe benefits, Recognition etc., It is against this premise that the adoption of Employee motivational factors became necessary in Nigeria Police Force to stimulate Service Quality. Conversely prior studies on Motivation, focuses on organization effectiveness, performance and productivity order than Service Quality thereby creating a lacuna in the area (Shoraj and Llaci 2015; Steadfast Opoku 2021; Amah and Nwuche 2013). Thus, this study targets to find the relationship between Employee motivation and Service Quality level of Nigerian Police Force in the South-South region of Nigeria The Police Force is essential because of their duties to; protect lives and properties of citizens, prevent crimes, enforce Law and Order and administration of justice (Ogunsina, 2011).

Statement of the Problem

Police officers in Nigeria are subjected to criticism as a result of not meeting the obligations to the people and assigned responsibilities (Gholami & Abdulrauf, 2018).

These problems are rooted in the lack of Employee Motivation of the police in Nigeria to discharge their duties of protecting lives and property, which often causes a loss of lives and property (Badiora et al., 2020). The lack of Employee Motivation for police officers in Nigeria has also resulted in fraudulent acts and practices and lowers the Quality of the job performance of the police officers in the South-South, Nigeria (Umar et al., 2013).

There are misapplication and misuse of Funds, insufficient financial and non-financial benefits, Poor salary structure, Delayed Gratuities, Poor working Environment and Tools, Poor relationships amongst Commanders and subordinates, Tribalism, non-utilization of trained police personnel in their special areas of training, and wrong procedures in training, selection, and placement after training (Badiora et al., 2020). Understanding the complex interactions that influence human behavior and organizational practice can help improve police practices in Nigeria (Oduntan, 2017). There is a responsibility on the Nigeria Police leadership to ensure that employee motivation is of the highest possible standard, especially welfare, pay and conditions, health and safety, empowerment, motivation, personal development, discipline, etc. to secure high performance via Service Quality. A strong Motivational Techniques, supported by appropriate structures and systems, must become part of the command style of leadership in the Nigeria Police to solve problems and increase overall organizational performance as Service Quality increases (Oduntan, 2017). Prior studies has shown that Nigeria police Officers has been experiencing low level of Service Quality (Andrew et al 2022) Of these studies in Nigeria, very few assessed the influence of Extrinsic and intrinsic motivation On Service Quality in the Nigeria Police Force of Rivers State. Rather they focused on the Educational Sector, Financial Sector and the Health Sector in Nigeria. Hence the need for this study to empirically analyze how extrinsic and intrinsic motivational tools can be used in the Nigerian Police Force in the South-South, to effectively improve Service Quality in the face of the current economic challenges in Nigeria.

THE AIM AND OBJECTIVES STUDY

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between employee motivation and Service Quality of Nigerian police force in the South-South. Specifically, the objectives seek to;

- i). Ascertain the relationship between intrinsic Motivation and Service Quality of Nigerian
- ii). Police force in the South-South.
- iii) Examine the relationship between Extrinsic Motivation and Service Quality of Nigerian police force in the South-South

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In line with the specific objectives, the following research questions are raised.

- i). How does intrinsic factor relate to Service Quality of Nigerian police force in the South- South?
- ii.) How does Extrinsic factors relate to Service Quality of Nigerian police force in the South-South?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Based on the research questions above, the following research hypotheses are formulated.

H01: There is no significant relationship between intrinsic factors and Service Quality of Nigerian police force in the South-South

H02: Extrinsic factors have no significant relationship with Service Quality of Nigerian police force in the South-South.

LITERATURE REVIEW

EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION

The word motivation originated from the concept of motive which describes an individual's drives and needs that are essential to achieve certain desires (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2012). Several definitions of motivation were seen in previous researches. According to Maduka and Okafor (2014), motivation refers to the willingness of an individual to put greater efforts to attain particular goals. Therefore, the concept of motivation stresses on an individual's feeling of enthusiasm and attentiveness to be able to achieve his or her goals in an effective manner. Correspondingly, Robbins (2001) reported that the motivation of an individual represents the energies that could inspire, direct, and maintain or enhance his/ her efforts. Motivation was also previously expressed as an internal inner wish that exists within an employee to accomplish his or her tasks successfully, because such tasks are exciting and match his or her interests (Gouws, 1995).

Employee motivation can be expressed according to the inner desire of an individual to exemplify his or her capabilities to achieve certain goals for an expected reward. Motivation is an art with a purpose to get individuals to work willingly, and influencing them to behave in a certain manner to accomplish their tasks (Maduka & Okafor, 2014). Certain scholars (Coetsee, 2002; Robbins, Judge, Odendaal & Roodt, 2009) demonstrated that employees' motivation at the work place appears through their willingness to effectively use their knowledge and skills to achieve the desired organizational objectives in relation to their satisfaction

and needs. Motivation is one of the key issues for any organization either public or private (Muogbo, 2013; Zameer, Ali, Nisar, & Amir, 2014). Particularly, in order to drive the success of an organization, motivation has a significant role. Chintallo and Mahadeo (2013) revealed that all organizations, including the public or private sector encounter the issue of employee motivation. In the previous literature, it was reported that there are several key elements which can enhance the commitment of employees towards an organization. The factors included salaries and wages, job security, promotion, and bonus (Zameer et al., 2014). Reward are also some of the key strategies to reinforce employees' motivation to utilize their best capabilities to come up with innovative ideas that could improve the functionality of business and further increase organizational performance either financially or non-financially (Aktar et al., 2012; Kawara, 2014; Roos, 2005).

DIMENSIONS OF EMPLOYEES MOTIVATION

Intrinsic Factors

Intrinsic motivation is defined as the performance of an activity for its inherent satisfactions rather than for some separable outcome, reflecting the natural disposition in humans to assimilate and learn (Ryan & Deci, 2000). It refers to when employees engage in an activity out of interest, for the sake of the activity, and for the satisfaction that the experience of engaging in that activity will bring to them (Lin, 2007). Behaviors that are intrinsically motivated are thus engaged in for their own sake, and not for any other outcome (Cerasoli et al., 2014). Prior research have indicated that increased intrinsic motivation can be related to employee willingness to create a positive mood, in turn leading to increased learning and knowledge sharing (Lin, 2007). Employees are intrinsically motivated for some activities and not for others, and it has been observed that not everyone is motivated by the same activities (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Many researchers and theories confirm that intrinsic motivators can be more effective than extrinsic ones in motivating employees (Nasri & Charfeddine, 2012; Giancola, 2014). Some previous research that has suggested that intrinsic rewards are superior to extrinsic ones has done so with the reasoning that employees perceive them as a more certain outcome of performing a task than extrinsic outcomes (Nasri & Charfeddine, 2012).

Because intrinsic motivation exists in the connection between an employee and a task, some researchers have defined intrinsic motivation in terms of the task that is performed by the employee, while others have defined intrinsic motivation in terms of the satisfaction an employee gains from performing the task (Ryan & Deci, 2000). An example of intrinsic motivation is how self-

fulfilled an employee feels as a result of performing a task well (Nasri & Charfeddine, 2012). Renko et al. (2012) write that an employee who looks to learn and grow as a person while working, due to the work itself, is motivated by intrinsic rewards. Research on altruism has showed that people enjoy helping others, and that intrinsic motivators played an important role in explaining human behavior (Lin, 2007). Cerasoli et al. (2014) further stated that when extrinsic motives are weak or absent, intrinsic motivation will become the only functional driver of performance. It has also been suggested that an efficient staff can be obtained by recruiting proactive employees, with high self-esteem and that are intrinsically motivated (Lin, 2007). Motivation is thus further dissected by distinguishing between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The general distinction made between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is that while intrinsic motivation is driven by forces from within oneself, extrinsic motivation is driven by outside forces (Giancola, 2014). In connection to the work environment an employee would be intrinsically motivated by performing a task depending on the extent that the particular task is —interesting, challenging, and has personal meaning based on the satisfaction they receive from performing the activity itself (Giancola, 2014).

Extrinsic Factors

In contrast to intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation on the other hand pertains whenever an activity is performed in order to obtain some separable outcome (Ryan & Deci, 2000). There are varied types of extrinsic motivation, some represent active states in employees while others represent impoverished forms of motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Extrinsic motivation can vary depending on how autonomous it is; an employee may perform a task because of fear of being punished or fired, or the employee can perform an activity because this activity will lead to a promotion, bonus, or raise in the future (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Both activities include external instrumentalities but vary in autonomy; the first one involves more of an obligation to an external control, whereas the second one also involves personal endorsement and the employee's choice (Ryan & Deci, 2000). From the perspective of extrinsic motivation, employee behavior is driven by the perceived benefits of the action that he or she will perform, or the anticipation of instrumental gain or loss (Lin, 2007; Cerasoli et al., 2014).

However, it has also been argued that extrinsic motivation varies considerably and can reflect external control or true self-regulation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Extrinsic Motivation can be engendered by a number of social–environmental factors, including expected reward, expected evaluation, competition, surveillance, time limits, and external control over task engagement (Amabile, 1996; Deci & Ryan, 1985). Some goal-or-

constraint-oriented motivators can be internalized over time such that they no longer feel like they come from outside the person. Rather, they can become part of an individual's identity and sense of self. Some researchers (Deci & Ryan, 1985) continue to consider these motivators as extrinsic because they set up tasks as means to an end rather than emphasize the enjoyable experience of the task itself. The main goal of behaviors from employees who are extrinsically motivated is thus to receive organizational rewards or benefits from the achievement of an organizational goal or task (Lin, 2007). Extrinsic outcomes are the rewards that are distributed by some external agent in the organization, where an example could be the monetary reward that an employee receives for putting in extra effort at work, job security, and promotions (Nasri & Charfeddine, 2012; Lin, 2007). This implies that organizational rewards are useful for employees who are extrinsically motivated in order for them to perform desired behaviors (Lin, 2007). However, previous research has suggested that extrinsic rewards only secure temporary compliance (Lin, 2007).

Service Quality

In the past few decades, researchers and practitioners directed a lot of attention to service quality (SQ) due to its strong effect on customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, business performance and profitability. SQ is usually defined as a measure of how well the delivered services level matches customer's expectations (Santos, 2003). As an example, Gronroos (1984) outlined perceived SQ, as "the outcome of an evaluation process, where the consumer compares his expectations with the service he perceives he has received". Furthermore, Parasuraman et al. (1988) defined SQ as the total evaluation of a specific service firm that comes from comparing the performance of that firm with the customers' general expectations of the firm's performance in that industry. Quality is something that almost everyone wants; thus, quality is a primary concern and the common denominator in the hospitality industry. Quality includes product or service quality (Glover, 1998). Parasuraman et al. (1985) defined service quality as a comparison between customers' expectations and actual performance. Service quality is considered as a significant core concept and a critical success in the hospitality industry. A successful hotel delivers excellent quality service to customers, and is considered the life of hotel (Al-Ababneh, 2017). Subsequent studies indicated that service quality is multidimensional, Service quality could be technical or functional or image (Gronroos, 1982, 2001), physical, corporate and interactive, (Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1982) service product, service environment, and service delivery (Rust & Oliver, 1994); interaction quality, physical environment quality, and outcome quality (Brady & Cronin, 2001).

Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) provided the most

commonly used SERVQUAL model with five dimensions. They include Reliability (Ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately), Responsiveness (Willingness to help customers and provide prompt service), Assurance (Knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence), Empathy (Caring, individualized attention the firm provides its customers) and Tangibles (Appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials). They equally proposed the SERVQUAL Scale which is the most popular instrument for measuring service quality. In another perspective, Kaplan and Norton (1992) prescribed service quality for guests in the hotel firms as: time, quality, performance and service, and cost. In a nutshell, the service quality evaluates the operational efficiency of the staff while meeting the guest expectations.

The usage of the SERVQUAL scale, presented by Parasuraman et al. (1988), pre-dominated the conceptualization and measurement of the SQ construct. Their measurement of SQ suggests a gap-based comparison of the performance perceptions and expectations of consumers. Grönroos (1984) proposed the first SQ model, and later other important researchers presented their own conceptualizations (e.g. Parasuraman et al., 1985, 1988, Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Dabholkar et al., 1996; Brady & Cronin, 2001).

Intrinsic Motivation and Service Quality

Intrinsic motivation is the motivation to do something for its own sake, for the sheer enjoyment of the task itself. Extrinsic motivation is the motivation to do something in order to attain some external goal or meet some externally imposed constraint. Theorists have emphasized the role of certain psychological states in the experience of intrinsic motivation, including a sense of self-determination, or perceived control over task engagement, that can serve to enhance self-perceptions of competence (Ryan & Deci, 2000). The highest level of intrinsic motivation has been labeled “optimal experience” or “flow” (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). Most descriptions of intrinsic motivation relate the doer to the task. Task motivation is seen to come from within the individual. Pleasure is gained from engagement in the task itself and often, too, from the challenge that the task presents. A sense of satisfaction comes from task completion. Intrinsic rewards or motivation as described by Richmond (2016), are those that are inherent in the essence of an employee or a position. Intrinsic rewards are those that are based on an employee's talent, recognition, trust, and achievement (Chiang & Birtch, 2018). Growth possibilities, a sense of success, social standing, recognition, fulfillment, self-esteem, a sense of autonomy, and a sense of responsibility are just a few examples of intrinsic rewards (Mahaney & Lederer, 2006). Having the ability to execute tough work, receiving feedback and

recognition, and being presented with possibilities for growth and development within their profession are all examples of intrinsic benefits that individuals can gain from their employment (Mottaz, 2005). The ability to provide results while remaining engaged, satisfied, and proud of their accomplishments will be demonstrated by these individuals (Mahaney & Lederer, 2006).

Organizational practices, according to Long and Shields (2010), have become increasingly prevalent as non-cash or intrinsic rewards have become more prevalent. Numerous firms that have introduced non-cash (intrinsic) rewards have the capability of rewarding both individual employees as well as groups and teams inside the organization through the use of these rewards. These intrinsic benefits, which acknowledge employees for their efforts, accomplishments, and high-quality work, help to guarantee that people are committed, engaged, and motivated in their jobs. People working in organizations now have a better opportunity to shape the structure of their organizations' reward systems (Allen & Killman, 2011).

It has been recommended by Sweins, Kalmi, and Hulkko-Nyman (2009) that organizations be forced to explain to their employees how their compensation system and organizational structure work. The ability to get more familiarity with a system is essential for ensuring that personnel understand their obligations.

Extrinsic Motivation and Service Quality

Extrinsic rewards are those that are unrelated to the job. They include compensation, fringe benefits, job security, promotions, private office space, and the work environment's social climate. Additionally, competitive salaries, pay increases, merit bonuses, and indirect forms of compensation such as compensatory time off are examples (Mahaney & Lederer 2006; Mottaz, 2005). According to Goldsmith, Veum, and Darity (2000), organizations remain competitive by constantly comparing their extrinsic rewards to those of competitors, ensuring higher levels of employee productivity, engagement, and commitment to the organization, as well as lower turnover. As a result, people gravitate toward well-compensated jobs, exert additional effort to perform tasks that earn them more money, and become agitated when their pay is threatened or reduced (Danish & Usman, 2010). Extrinsic rewards are used to demonstrate that the company takes team contributions to quality seriously.

Extrinsic reward systems are developed in accordance with the organizational process of establishing performance structures that determine the level of compensation for employees. As a result, it is critical that all employees view reward systems as equitable in terms of processes, rules, regulations, and award mechanisms (Hankin, 2015). According to Crystal and Gabi (2016), management decisions regarding employee

compensation should be rational and transparent. When employees believe their organization is being fair when it comes to extrinsic rewards, they commit to organizational performance and long-term development.

THEORITICAL Framework

Expectancy Theory.

This theory is propounded by Vroom (1964). The expectancy theory, in contrary to need theory, is a process related theory that focuses on different employee perceptions and thoughts and concerns how employees choose among alternative behaviors and levels of effort (George & Jones, 2012; Purvis et al., 2015). The theory puts particular focus on employees' personal assessments of the environment and actions as a consequence of their expectations (Purvis et al., 2015). The theory proposes two fundamental issues; the first is that regardless of the different available outcomes, an employee will only be motivated to contribute his or her inputs to the organization if they believe that the result will achieve a particular level of performance (George & Jones, 2012). In other words, if employees do not believe that they are able to perform at a certain level, the motivation to perform the given task will not be there (George & Jones, 2012). The second issue is that employees will only be motivated to perform at a certain level, if performing at this level will lead to desired outcomes (George & Jones, 2012).

Schedlitzki and Edwards (2014) link the path-goal theory to the assumptions of the expectancy theory and state that employees are more likely to perform well if they are confident that they are capable of executing a task, that they will achieve the outcome that is expected and that they will receive the outcome that is most valued by them. The expectancy theory explains that an employee will only be motivated to contribute and put effort into a task when the outcome of the two key factors is positive (George & Jones, 2012). This implies that the more positive outcomes are perceived to be linked with a particular action; the more willing an employee will be to perform this particular action (Vroom, 1964; cited in Lin, 2007).

Expectancy theory defines three main factors that determine the work motivation of an employee: valence, instrumentality, and expectancy (Estes & Polnick, 2012). The first factor, valence, refers to the value that a particular outcome has to an employee, and the desire to attain it (Estes & Polnick, 2012). An outcome is positively valent to an employee if they prefer attaining the particular outcome over not attaining it, whereas an employee would prefer to avoid an outcome that is negatively valent (Estes & Polnick, 2012). Vroom (1964; cited in Estes & Polnick, 2012) defines valence as a function of an employee's needs, values, goals, and

sources of motivation. According to Purvis et al. (2015), valence can be described as the degree of personal attractiveness of the rewards that follow the achievement of some organizational goals. An important distinction made is that valence is not the satisfaction of an outcome, but rather the anticipated satisfaction of a future outcome, acting as a motivator toward future action in expectancy theory (Vroom, 1964; cited in Burns et al., 2015). Valence can thus be a positive or negative outcome, and it may also vary in magnitude and size (George & Jones, 2012). The magnitude of the valence concerns how desirable or undesirable the outcome is for the employee, and as explained in need theory, employees will prefer and thus consider valent outcomes that satisfy their needs (George & Jones, 2012). Issues related to valence can occur because some outcomes that are highly valent are not available to employees (George & Jones, 2012).

Expectancy theory further proposes that outcomes should be linked to desired organizational behaviors or to levels of job performance (George & Jones, 2012). This related to instrumentality, the second factor of expectancy theory, which is the employee's perception and belief that first level outcomes will lead to second level outcomes (Vroom, 1964; Estes & Polnick, 2012). Instrumentality can also be described as an employee's perception of the probability of performing successfully if they provide their effort, development, and implement creativity and innovation in their work (Purvis et al., 2015). Like valence, instrumentality is thus oriented towards higher-order outcomes, and describes the degree to which a first level outcome will lead the way to a desired second level outcome (Burns et al., 2015; Parashar, 2016).

In other words, an employee will put high valence on performing at a high level when the employee believes that this high performance is instrumental in obtaining other rewarding outcomes (e.g. increase in wage), or if this high performance is instrumental in the avoidance of outcomes that the employee wants to avoid (Estes & Polnick, 2012). Just like with valence, instrumentality can be positive or negative, as well as vary in size and magnitude (George & Jones, 2012). Instrumentality is likely to be low when an employee perceives that valued rewards follow all levels of performance (Estes & Polnick, 2012). Instrumentalities that are high, where the employee believes that with a certain level of performance the desired outcome will be obtained, are effective in motivating employees (George & Jones, 2012).

Occasionally, despite that an employee perceives that a highly valent outcome will result directly from job performance; this employee can remain unmotivated to perform at high levels (George & Jones, 2012). This is where the third factor of the expectancy theory, expectancy, needs to be considered. Expectancy may be defined as "the momentary belief concerning the

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

S/N	Moderation Stage	RELAIONSHIP	STD.BETA	ACTUAL BETA	S.E	C.R	P	REMARK
1	→							
2	→ (HYPOTHESIS 2)	INTRINSIC MOTIVATION AND SERVICE QUALITY	0.780	6.082	0.20	3.07	0.0000	NOT SUPPORTED
3	→							
4	→							
5	→ (HYPOTHESIS 5)	EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION AND SERVICE QUALITY	0.900	14.035	0.27	3.62	0.000	NOT SUPPORTED
6	→							
7		ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE VS EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AND SERVICE QUALITY	0.604 0.683 0.681	0.73 0.82 1.411	0.52 0.61 0.53	2.07 2.25 1.98	0.000 0.000 0.000	

likelihood that a particular act will be followed by a particular outcome" (Vroom, 1964; cited in Estes & Polnick, 2012). This belief is commonly rooted in the individual employee's past experiences, self-efficacy and how difficult the performance standard or goal is perceived to be (Estes & Polnick, 2012).

Expectancy helps understand why motivation can be low even when different instrumentalities and valences are high, and is thus the perceived likelihood that an action, or personal effort, will lead to the intended outcome (Parashar, 2016). Expectancy thus explains that employees will be motivated to perform at desired levels only if they believe that they are able to do so, meaning that if employees believe that they will perform at a high level when they work hard, their expectancy will be high (George & Jones, 2012). It does not matter how valent or high instrumentality other factors are, if the employee believes that he or she cannot perform at a certain level, he or she will not be motivated to do so (George & Jones, 2012). This goes into the previously mentioned subject of self-efficacy, which explains that employees are not always certain that their efforts will result in a given level of performance (George & Jones, 2012).

Understanding the three factors in expectancy theory; valence, instrumentality, and expectancy, provides an insight into the nature and cause of employee participation in pursuing desired organizational outcomes (Purvis et al., 2015). Whereas the three perceptions can influence an employee's motivation individually, these perceptions can have a powerful effect on motivation if they are combined (Estes and Polnick, 2012). targets and describe the association.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross sectional survey design of the quasi-experimental research because it between the

variables. The target population comprises of the entire officers and men of Nigeria police force (NPF) domiciled in south-south Nigeria. Available data on the force official website indicates that the region has 52,579 officers and men in the South South.A census Population was adopted. So all States in the South- South were used as the Target/Accessible population. Taro Yamen formula was employed to determine the sample size of 397. The sampling technique that was applied in selecting a sample of 397 respondents from a population of fifty two thousand ,five hundred and seventy nine (52579) in this study was the cluster Sampling technique . The clusters here are the Police officers working in their respective State commands .Here every member has an equal chance of being selected..

The Operational Measures of Variable for Employee motivation, Service Quality and organizational culture was measured with items adopted from the works of Bergström and Martínez (2016) for intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors, Kamalanabhan, Sai and Mayuri (2009) and Hua, Horng and Sun (2009) for Service Quality and Denison and Mishra (1995) for the moderating variable (organizational culture)The face and content validity was used The instrument's reliability was determined using the Cronbach's Alpha test and SPSS software, in accordance with Nunnaly's (1978) model, which suggests a bench mark of 0.70.A pilot study was also conducted. The employed data were analysed using different statistical methods and regression analysis as undertaking using Structural Equation Modeling aided with AMOS22.0 Version.

DATA ANALYSIS

Three types of analysis were used to analyzed the responses on the structured questionnaire and research questions. The Univariate, Bivariate and Multivariate

Analysis and thereafter hypotheses testing; The table above shows the result of standardized and unstandardized regression estimate of the model.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Empirical findings from data analyzed inform the following conclusions as it concerns our study:

The aim of the study was to examine the relationship between Employee Motivation and Service Quality of Nigeria police Force in the South- South. The construct of Service Quality was extensively investigated in previous research studies in different domains; thus, results show that Employee Motivation affects the Service Quality of The Overall Workers in an Organisation. Based on this findings the following recommendation were made; The Federal government should see that Police Officers policing tools, vehicles are adequate and in a good working condition. This is a great extrinsic motivational tool that can enhance the Service Quality of Nigeria Police Force. Police officers due for promotion and allowances should be recognized without delays. And their Salary conditions should be improved by the Federal Government. This is a high intrinsic Motivational tool that has a potency of increasing Service Quality of Employees.

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